

MOTIVATION OF ACCOUNTING, BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT (ABM) COLLEGE FRESHMEN STUDENTS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN GENERAL EDUCATION 5

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive correlational study aimed to explore the structural relationship among the constructs of motivation and the academic achievement of Accounting, Business, and Management freshmen college students in the General Education 5 (GE 5) subject. The respondents were 140 students from the College of Accounting Education, and the College of Business and Administration Education (ABM) of the University of Mindanao. This study used the Science Motivation Questionnaire to measure the level of the constructs of motivation, and the score in the final examination to measure the level of the academic achievement of the respondents. Findings showed that ABM college freshmen were highly motivated to learn the concepts in GE 5. They see that learning the subject is meaningful, engaging, and relevant to their lives and goals. On average, ABM college freshmen have achieved the competencies set by CHED for the subject. All three core competencies in the subject were achieved by most of the students. There was no significant structural relationship between the level of motivation and the level of achievement among ABM college freshmen students in the GE 5 subject. The level of motivation has nothing to do with the scores of the respondents in their final examinations. Instructors teaching the subject are encouraged to make important modifications and adjustments in their strategies, methodologies, and approaches to raise their students' self-determination and self-efficacy.

Keywords: *Motivation, ABM college students, GE 5, Science Motivation Questionnaire, Structural Relationship*

INTRODUCTION

Ever since the first graduates of the K-12 curriculum have entered the tertiary level, college science for nonscience majors has undergone consequent changes. The purpose of these changes is to cater to the needs of the degree program so as to avoid redundancy in the topics with the senior high science. Like all minor subjects in tertiary for Accounting, Business, and Management (ABM) aligned courses, Science, Technology, and Society (General Science 5) is dealt with less priority. As a result, students are poorly motivated in learning science resulting in low academic achievement. They do not see the relevance of science to their careers.

The issue of motivation vis-à-vis academic achievement of nonscience major freshmen students in science subjects is globally widespread. Motivation has already been identified to be a key process or mechanism in science to enhance students' overall achievement (Lazowski & Hulleman, 2016). The crux of the issue is that freshmen college students are especially susceptible to the changes and conflicts that arise from motivation in learning scientific concepts that they did not study in high school or are new to them. If low motivation is left unchecked in these students, this leads to adverse outcomes in their achievements during their school career. This can trigger further low enthusiasm and a spiral downward of demoralization (Potvin & Hasni, 2014).

In the Southeast Asian region, the lack of motivation of most college students is not new to the tertiary education landscape, especially with general education subjects. According to the reports of performance in science learning in Malaysia, it is found that students' lack of motivation towards science learning has a considerable impact on students' scientific attitude and achievement overall. Poor motivation in freshmen students often leads to low achievement (Chan & Norlizah, 2017).

In the pursuit of the ongoing education reforms in the Philippines that included the shift to the K-12 curriculum, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has revised the General Education (GE) curriculum to expose undergraduate students to various domains of knowledge and ways of comprehending social and natural realities, developing in the process, intellectual competencies and civic responsibilities (CMO No. 20, series of 2013). This resulted in a complete overhaul of science-related subjects for nonscience major students like life sciences and physical sciences. Since the implementation of the STS under the course title General Education 5 (GE 5) is relatively in the early stage, there is now a need to study this area to improve the strategies, methodologies, instruction, and approaches in the GE 5-STS that develop and promote motivation to ensure continuous and high achievement. In addition to that, no motivational research involving nonscience major students such as ABM-aligned freshmen students has ever been conducted.

At many colleges in the Philippines, science for nonscience majors often has hundreds of students enrolled in each section, making it challenging to address the specific needs of individuals. The University of Mindanao, for example, boasts a population of more than 35,000 undergraduate students in the academic year 2018-2019. With its nine campuses and branches in Mindanao, it is not surprising just like all other tertiary level schools that not all freshmen students are allowed to learn GE 5-STS individually and to their liking.

They must be assessed on what drives them to learn subjects outside of their concentration. A shared challenge, therefore, for instructors of science at all institutions, particularly those with large enrollment classes, is to motivate nonscience majors to learn science successfully. One of the most important goals of an instructor of introductory college science courses is to help freshmen students become motivated self-learners to ensure high achievement (Glyn, Brickman, Armstrong, & Taasobshirazi, 2011).

Science and technology are perceived as fundamental forces behind economic development in industrialized nations (Chan & Norlizah, 2017). The Philippines, as a developing country, should be prepared to join the ranks of developed nations, so students and college graduates alike need to excel in science and technology. Since the General Education – Science, Technology, and Society (GE 5-STS) curriculum is relatively new from its implementation, and not much is known about its impact on nonscience majors especially with the ABM-aligned courses, there is now a compelling reason to identify what motivates a nonscience major to learn science, technology, and society to improve the strategies, methodologies, instruction, and approaches in the said subject. To date, no motivational research involving ABM-aligned students in relation to the new GE 5-STS subject has ever been conducted. In particular, this study seeks to determine the level of the different constructs of motivations possessed by these freshmen and their achievement as they learn the lessons in the GE 5-STS. The results of this study would provide a better understanding of the motivating factors of students at the tertiary level in general. The curriculum would be streamlined and tailored if the need arises, leaning more toward the best interest of students. Furthermore, this would offer significant insights to instructors and curriculum developers for areas of improvement, revisions, or modifications to the current curriculum and trends in GE 5-STS.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study is to determine the level of different constructs of motivation among Accounting, Business, and Management first-year college students, who are currently enrolled in the General Education 5 curriculum at the University of Mindanao and establish a structural relationship between these constructs of motivation and their academic achievement in GE 5.

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the motivation of Accounting, Business, and Management college freshmen students in terms of:
 - 1.1. intrinsic motivation;
 - 1.2. extrinsic motivation;
 - 1.3. goal orientation;
 - 1.4. self-determination; and
 - 1.5. self-efficacy?

2. What is the level of academic achievement among Accounting, Business, and Management college freshmen students in General Education 5 in terms of:
 - 2.1. intellectual competencies;
 - 2.2. personal and civic responsibilities; and

2.3. application and practical skills?

3. Is there a structural relationship between the level of motivation and the level of academic achievement among Accounting, Business, and Management college freshmen students in GE 5?

The following hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H0: There is no structural relationship between the level of motivation and the level of academic achievement among Accounting, Business, and Management college freshmen students in GE 5.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at the University of Mindanao (UM) Bolton and Matina Campuses. These branches of the university are strategically located in the downtown area of Davao City and have the highest number of enrollees among all the branches of UM in Mindanao. The University of Mindanao was chosen because it is the largest private university in Mindanao and is hailed as the institution with the second-highest number of programs accredited by PACUCOA in the country today.

This study also used the simple random sampling method. The principle of a simple random sampling technique is that every object has the same probability of being chosen. The aim is to reduce the potential for human bias in the selection of cases to be included in the sample. As a result, the simple random sample provides us with a sample that is highly representative of the population being studied (Kuswando, 2019). In this method, every college freshman in the research locale enrolled under the GE 5 subject has an equal chance of being included in the sample. These respondents were all enrolled in the first term of the second semester in the academic year 2019 – 2020. The respondents in this study were 140 college freshmen from the College of Accounting Education and the College of Business and Administration Education of the University of Mindanao. These students previously completed the Accounting, Business, and Management (ABM) strand in Senior High School; hence, the respondents are collectively tagged as ABM college freshmen students. Using Microsoft Excel spreadsheets, a number was assigned to their names in the class record. The software generated a number between 0 to the maximum number of students in the class record with no duplicates using the algorithm =RANDBETWEEN(0,maximum number of students + 1). To produce the respondents representing every course under the accounting, business, and management degree program, only the students with numbers 1 to 20 were selected.

Furthermore, this study used the descriptive correlational research design. Descriptive correlational research primarily aims to describe the relationship among variables rather than to infer cause-and-effect relationships (Wetherington, 2010). Using this research design, this present study is focused on describing the relationship between the constructs of motivation and the academic achievement of the respondents.

In order to guarantee systematic order in data collection, the researcher requested permission to conduct the study from the graduate school and the institution through

formal letters. The researcher administered the questionnaire in person after a brief introduction and instruction. \ The researcher reiterated the Informed Consent to all the respondents. The respondents followed the guidelines on the questionnaires. After the allotted time, the questionnaires were systematically collected by the researcher. As for the final test material, the usual protocol of the school was followed. The conduct of the final test examination and the collection of the test materials were commenced in a regular manner.

After the collection of the questionnaires and the final test material, the results were sorted and tabulated. Subsequently, the data were subjected to statistical analysis using statistical tools. The researcher interpreted the results of the statistical analysis in conjunction with the research hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The structural relationship was interpreted based on the value obtained from the statistical analysis of the SEM package.

To interpret the relationship among the multiple indicators for both independent and dependent variables, Multiple Regression through Structural Equation Modeling was used. The objective of multiple regression analysis is to use the independent variables whose values are known to predict the value of the single dependent value (Cohen et al., 2013). This research design helped the researcher to establish a structural relationship among the indicators of motivation and the achievement of ABM graduates in the GE 5 subject.

In order to measure the level of motivation of the respondents, the Science Motivation Questionnaire (SMQ) by Glynn and Koballa (2006) was used. This survey questionnaire was composed of 30 questions that were grouped according to the five constructs of motivation as indicators, namely: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, goal orientation, self-determination, and self-efficacy. This was a pre-constructed questionnaire; however, to suit the purpose of the study, the responses and several words used in the items were reworded to fit the purpose of the study, such as the word “science” becoming “science, technology, and society.” The researcher sent an e-mail to the owner of the questionnaire, asking permission to use the instrument.

To ensure the reliability and suitability of the instrument, the SMQ was also validated by two experts from the panel of examiners and an external validator. The reliability test result from the Institutional Research Office of the Holy Cross of Davao College, Inc. yielded a 0.83 Chronbach’s alpha rating. Values equal to or above 0.70 correspond to acceptable internal consistency (Hoekstra et al., 2019).

On the questionnaire, students would respond to each item on a rating scale of 5 to 1: very highly motivating (5), highly motivating (4), moderately motivating (3), lowly motivating (2), or very lowly motivating (1). This questionnaire provides college instructors with a tool for efficiently gathering data that can increase the effectiveness of advisement sessions with students. It also provides researchers with an instrument for investigating students’ motivation to learn science in college courses, the relationship of motivation to other student characteristics, and the interaction of motivation with instructional methods (Glyn, Brickman, Armstrong, & Taasobshirazi, 2011). A Likert scale was prepared to

analyze and interpret the data for the level of motivation of the respondents; the scale has an equal interval of 0.49 starting from 1.00.

In order to measure the level of achievement of ABM college freshmen students in GE-5, the score in the final examination of the respondents was used. The final test material was given in the first term of the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020 last January 16 to 17, 2020. The final examination was composed of 60 multiple-choice questions. The number of items was divided into the three core areas of competencies in the GE 5-STS subject as indicators, namely, (a) Intellectual Competencies, (b) Personal and Civic Responsibilities, and (c) Application and Practical Skills. Hence, each competency corresponded to 20 questions in the examination. These competencies are set by the CHED for the subject as part of the new curriculum for the incoming freshmen for the school year 2018-2019 and graduates of the K to 12 program of the government (CMO No. 20, s. 2013).

RESULTS

The Level of Motivation of ABM College Freshmen Students

Table 1 presents the level of motivation of the Accounting, Business, and Management (ABM) college freshmen in each of the five constructs of motivation. The data were collected using the Science Motivation Questionnaire (SMQ).

Table 1. The Level of Motivation of the Accounting, Business, and Management College Freshmen Students

	N	Mean	Level of Motivation
Intrinsic motivation	140	4.26	High
Extrinsic motivation	140	3.89	High
Goal orientation	140	3.52	High
Self-determination	140	3.31	Moderate
Self-efficacy	140	3.40	Moderate

Data from the table reveal that the level of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and goal orientation was altogether high in 140 randomly selected ABM freshmen students. Meanwhile, their level of self-determination and self-efficacy were both moderate. In general, the results showed that the level of motivation of the majority of the freshmen students in the GE 5 - STS subject was high. In particular, among the five constructs of motivation, intrinsic motivation garnered the highest mean score of 4.26.

Level of Achievement among ABM College Freshmen Students in General Education 5 - Science, Technology, and Society

Table 2 shows the level of achievement of ABM college freshmen students obtained from the scores in their final examinations, which were subjected to statistical treatment. The data were taken from the examination results using the SEM package software.

Table 2. The Level of Achievement of ABM College Freshmen Students

	N	Mean	Level of Achievement
Intellectual Competencies	140	3.19	Moderate
Personal and Civic Responsibilities	140	2.66	Moderate
Application and Practical Skills	140	2.65	Moderate

The results show that the level of achievement of ABM college freshmen students in their final examination was at a moderate level in all three (3) core competencies in the STS subject. The highest mean was obtained from the items under Intellectual Competencies (3.19), followed by Personal and Civic Responsibilities (2.66), and Application and Practical Skills (2.65), respectively.

Structural Relationship between the Level of Motivation and the Level of Achievement among ABM College Freshmen Students in General Education 5 -Science, Technology, and Society

Table 3 shows the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) results between the level of motivation and the level of achievement among ABM college freshmen students. All the necessary data from the SMQ and the final examination were set as inputs for the structural equation modeling (SEM) package software to determine the structural relationship between the two variables. The figure for structural r determines whether or not there is a significant structural relationship between the variables.

Table 3. Structural Relationship between Motivation and Achievement of the Students

Structural r	N	p-value	Decision on Ho
-.045 ^{NS}	140	.595	Accept Ho

NS - Not significant

The table shows the structural r-value of -0.045 and the p-value of 0.595, which prompts the researcher to accept the null hypothesis of this study. This means that there is no significant structural relationship between the level of motivation and the level of

achievement among ABM college freshmen students. The five constructs of motivation do not relate to the three core competencies in the GE 5 - STS.

DISCUSSION

The overall high level of motivation indicates that ABM college freshmen students responded positively to the questions that evoke motivation in learning GE 5 - STS concepts. A high level of intrinsic motivation means that ABM college freshmen students see that learning the lessons in the GE 5 - STS is meaningful, engaging, interesting, and relevant to their lives. Although the GE 5 - STS is a general education subject intended for all freshmen regardless of their degree program, freshmen students under the ABM courses nevertheless were enjoying the subject for the most part. It is inferred that these students drive themselves to learn because of the satisfaction they get to have when they participate in the GE 5 class, and the enjoyment they feel in the subject. The result generally points out that these students have the innate drive to learn the subject.

The same can be said for extrinsic motivation and goal orientation. The results mean that learning the concepts in the GE 5 is rewarding among ABM college freshmen students. They also understand that their learning in the subject relates to their personal goals and careers. A high level of both extrinsic motivation and goal orientation suggests that these students give importance to the rewards they get in learning GE 5, such as good grades in the subject, a job related to their course in science and technology, or a career in the future. It is inferred that the respondents personally believe that learning the concepts in the GE 5 - STS is valuable for their chosen career. The instrumental value of the lessons they learn at the end of the subject would heavily influence their goals. They see learning GE 5 - STS as a means to an end.

The results of this study are consistent with the findings of Libao et al. (2016), Nacionales et al. (2015), and Chan and Norlizah (2017) in that these constructs of motivation, as mentioned above, are the most fundamental processes that most students possess to drive their own learning in science subjects. Research about intrinsic and extrinsic motivation revealed that science subjects are mostly understood and appreciated better with these constructs of motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2020). The same claims are advanced in the recent study of Orhan-Ozen (2017) in that ABM-aligned students are intrinsically and extrinsically motivated to learn science. The result of this study regarding goal orientation is also similar to the findings of Glynn and his colleagues (2011), the forerunners of the SMQ. Goal orientation is also found to be high in nonscience major students taking up college science. The same observations made by Taasobshirazi and Sinatra (2011) led to the conclusion that more often than not, college students studying science are highly goal-oriented.

As for the two constructs of motivation, namely, self-determination and self-efficacy, they were found to be at a moderate level among ABM college freshmen students. Generally, self-determination is their responsibility for learning GE 5 - STS. Self-efficacy, on the other hand, is their confidence in learning GE 5 - STS. A moderate level of self-determination means that the respondents believe that they are in control of their own learning

experience to some extent, as in the study of Bassi and Delle Fave (2012). This further implies that freshmen students under the ABM courses assume that the efforts and the time they spend studying GE 5 - STS drive them to learn, more or less. They may acknowledge their obligation to prepare and study the lessons in the subject.

Meanwhile, a moderate level of self-efficacy denotes that ABM college freshmen students are self-assured to some degree that they can achieve well in GE 5 - STS. Self-efficacy also determines what goals these students choose to pursue, long-term and short-term, and how they go about accomplishing those goals. The result also implies that they have a moderate interest in the activities and tasks in the GE 5 - STS, which they are confident of achieving. This generally points out that if students believe that they can do it, they will do it in their own capacity (Ozgen & Bindaka, 2011). A learner with a high level of self-efficacy for a given task will be resilient and persistent in the face of setbacks, while a learner with low levels of self-efficacy for that task may disengage or avoid the situation (Van Dinther et al., 2011). On average, these students believe in their capacity to understand the lessons in the GE 5 – STS.

The data indicate that, on average, the respondents have grasped and comprehended the general concepts in the GE 5 - STS subject. CHED Memo no. 20, series of 2013 had intended that students taking up the GE 5 - STS subject shall have achieved the competencies that engage students to confront the realities brought about by science and technology in society by the time they finished the subject. It is inferred that the respondents have achieved critical-thinking and analytical skills in evaluating texts, written or visual, in the GE 5 - STS more or less. Further, they have understood their civic responsibilities as demanded by the community where they live and make decisions based on moral norms and imperatives on a moderate level. The result also implies that they mostly understood basic work-related skills and knowledge as a consequence of learning GE 5 - STS concepts.

The grade of students at the tertiary level in most universities and colleges is mostly based on the student's achievement in their final examination. In turn, the level of achievement of these freshmen students in terms of their final examination could substantially affect their final grades in the subject. The number of respondents who passed or failed the GE 5 - STS final examinations was found to be 61% or 81/140, more than half of the number of respondents. As per institutional policy of the University of Mindanao, all non-laboratory 3-unit courses such as STS shall follow a based-15 grading system. Final examinations are given 30% weight in the student's final grade. Therefore, in order to pass a 60-item examination, a student must obtain a score of 43. Among those who took the exam, the highest score was 53 out of 60, or equivalent to 90.08% in the based-15 grading system. Meanwhile, the lowest score was 31 out of 60, or equivalent to 57.50% in the same grading system.

Among the respondents, only one (1) respondent failed in the GE 5 - STS subject during the whole duration of the study. By large, the score in the final examination substantially affects the final grade of the respondents, because the former is given the highest percentage in the University of Mindanao's grading system than any other component

such as quizzes or assignments. However, failure in the subject has many contributory factors such as nonsubmission of requirements, failure to participate in school activities, frequent absences, and among others. The average final grade of all the respondents was 85.63 or 2.5 in the university's grading system. The highest grade was 93 or 1.8, and the lowest grade was 73, for which a grade of 7.5 was automatically given.

These findings agreed with the results of the study by Castillo (2017) in that ABM-aligned students, such as in accounting courses, are competent generally as reflected in the current trends in their performance in the board exams and the passing rate of universities and colleges. In the study of Zhernovnikova, Nalivayko, and Chornous (2017), a moderate level of intellectual and skills competence is manifested by students who understand the meaning and the importance of an activity in which they actively participate. All of the competencies determined by the CHED in its memorandum for General Education courses are set to instill reflective knowledge in the students that they can live the good life and display ethical decision-making in the face of scientific and technological advancement (CMO no. 20, s. 2013).

The figures in the table further imply that motivation has nothing to do with the achievement of students. Although the majority of the ABM college freshmen students have obtained a passing mark in their final examinations, this does not mean that motivation played an essential role in their success in the said examination. It indicates that the moderate level of motivation did not significantly influence the scores of the students in their final examination. The core competencies set by CHED namely, intellectual competencies, civic and personal responsibilities, and skills and application, did not have a significant interdependence with the overall level of motivation of the respondents who were enrolled in the academic year 2019 to 2020.

Most of the studies show that motivation has a relationship with students' achievement (Gupta & Mili, 2016; Sikhwari, 2014; Amrai et al., 2011). In the purview of education, it has been widely known that the motivation of learners affects achievement in academics. However, the result of this research finds support with the findings of Stofile (2017) and Sarangi (2015) in that the achievement of the students has no significant relationship with their level of motivation. The uniqueness of the circumstance, the variables, and the parameters of this study may have contributed to the results.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are presented:

Foremost, the moderate level of motivation among ABM college freshmen students in the subject Science, Technology, and Society indicates that they see that learning the concepts, theories, history, and the lessons in the subject as a whole is stimulating and rewarding. As reflected in the level of their intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, ABM college freshmen have the innate drive already to fuel their minds to grasp the lessons. They also give importance to the external rewards they get in learning GE 5 - STS. The level of their goal orientation means that they see that GE 5 - STS lessons relate to their personal

goals, ambitions, and careers at present and in the future. Furthermore, they believe that they have control over their learning, more or less. They also have moderate confidence that they can achieve good scores and do better in every activity, assignment, and challenge in the GE 5 -STS subject.

Secondly, the moderate level of achievement among ABM college freshmen students in the GE 5 - STS subject implies that they have understood the general concepts for the subject. This means, on average, that ABM college freshmen students have achieved the competencies set by CHED. It also suggests that they have intellectual competence, civic and personal responsibilities, and skills required in the GE 5 - STS. They have attained an understanding that scientific knowledge and technological development happen in the context of a society with all its socio-political, cultural, economic, and philosophical underpinnings at play.

Thirdly, the findings supported the null hypothesis that there is no significant structural relationship between the level of motivation and the level of achievement among ABM college freshmen students. This suggests that motivation has nothing to do with the level of their achievement in the subject. It also means that motivation, as the independent variable, neither correlates nor influences the score of the respondents in their final examinations and, ultimately, their final grade in the GE 5 - STS subject. A moderate level of motivation, as a result, did not lead to a moderate level of achievement among the ABM college freshmen in GE 5 – STS. Still, the researcher believes that instructors must cultivate positive motivation in every learner in their academic endeavors.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded:

Among the five constructs of motivation, the level of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and goal orientation was high among ABM college freshmen students. The other two constructs were moderate. From these results, instructors teaching the subject GE 5 - STS could make important modifications and adjustments in their strategies, methodologies, and approaches to raise their students' self-determination and self-efficacy. As for intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and goal orientation, instructors could also opt to sustain what they usually do in the classroom. Should they choose to make adjustments, instructors could do and adopt the following as classroom routines during the GE 5 - STS class:

- (a) *Give a sense of control.* Whereas guidance from a teacher is vital to keeping students on task and motivated, allowing students to have some choice and control over what happens in the classroom is a way to keep them engaged. For instance, allowing students to choose the type of task they do or the problems they have to focus on can give them a sense of control that can only motivate them to do more. This, in turn, would raise their self-determination. Self-determination can be supported by providing opportunities for students to be challenged.

- (b) *Let there be an occasional change in the learning environment.* A classroom is a usual place for learning. However, sitting at a desk day in and day out can make school start to seem a bit dull for some students. To renew interest in the subject matter, giving students a chance to get out of the classroom would keep them engaged. College students are usually in a classroom setting for a whole semester for minor subjects. GE 5 - STS is a subject that deals with not only pure science concepts but also with societal issues that overlap with the use of technology. Taking field trips, bringing in speakers, or even just heading to the library for some research would help ABM freshmen students establish their connection to the subject. The learner's brain loves novelty, and a new setting can be just what some students need to be inspired to achieve more.
- (c) *Make goals high but attainable.* Students tend to stay in their own comfort zone and do not seek to push themselves on their own if nobody pushes them to do more than the bare minimum. Most students like to be challenged and will work to meet high expectations as long as goals are within their reach. Instructors should not be afraid to push students to get more out of them. ABM college freshmen students are non-science majors, so it is natural for them to see GE 5 - STS as trivial and less important to their careers. Therefore, instructors should always remind their students of the goals they have and relay how the concepts in GE 5 - STS can help to achieve them. This will help raise their self-determination and self-efficacy.
- (d) *Be inspirational.* Inspirational teachers represent success to their students. Once students decide on their own success, they pay close attention to the behaviors, choices, and even sacrifices that lead to success. These behaviors include hard work, willingness to struggle, and the ability to learn from mistakes. Students internalize a teacher's behaviors, according to the Social Learning Theory of Bandura (2001), and strategies as a way to accomplish their own goals. Instructors should allow them to do so in their everyday routines, assignments, and encounters with their students. ABM college students are diverse and unique in terms of goals and motivation. GE 5 - STS curriculum developers should also incorporate more concepts of actual and daily life examples in most of the topics.
- (e) *Develop meaningful and respectful relationships with students.* If teachers are going to inspire and motivate all of their students truly, they should know each of them on a personal level. Teachers need to know their interests and hobbies, whom they hang out with, their family situations, and what gets them excited. As stated, ABM college students are diverse and unique in terms of goals and motivation. They all learn differently. In each classroom, several types of learners exist: visual, tactile, verbal, and more reserved, according to Gardner in his Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983). Each student will require different motivational strategies, and teachers will need to know them so they can predict what strategies might and could work. GE 5 - STS covers technological and societal issues. This is an essential responsibility of a GE 5 - STS instructor to discover their students' learning styles by knowing them and endeavor to teach them accordingly. This work will result in a teacher's ability to know their students, which leads to a more motivated, open learning community.

- (f) *Encourage self-reflection.* Many students want to succeed; they need help figuring out what they need to do in order to get there. One way to motivate students is to get them to take a hard look at themselves and determine their own strengths and weaknesses. Determining strengths and weaknesses develops self-confidence. This process, in turn, enhances their self-efficacy. GE 5 - STS is a subject that concerns environmental dilemmas and societal conflicts with the use of technology. Instructors and curriculum developers may include activities that focus on self-reflection and self-critique in the GE 5 - STS subject. Students are often much more motivated by creating these kinds of critiques of themselves than by having a teacher do it for them, as it makes them feel in charge of creating their own objectives and goals.

In conclusion, for this study, motivation did not relate to achievement. Although educational researchers and practitioners all agree that motivation is one of the most critical factors in learning (Orhan-Özen, 2017), other latent and quantifiable factors should also be taken into consideration to measure students' overall achievement. Students who are motivated to learn will continue to be interested and pay attention. As a result, they are willing to make an effort and take the necessary time to learn, focusing and devoting to the subjects, not giving up doing required behavior under challenging circumstances, insisting on bringing it to an end, and resolutions are then observed. Based on the preceding discussion and findings, it is an absolute imperative for instructors and curriculum developers to incorporate lessons, strategies, methodologies, and approaches that develop and promote motivation and employ said contingents to ensure continuous and high achievement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers are responsible for protecting the participants in their studies and ensuring that their research does not harm them in any way. Ethical conduct is essential for ensuring the safety and well-being of research participants (Cacciattolo, 2015). Adhering to ethical norms during the course of research is of utmost importance to uphold a study's integrity and credibility. This Ethical Consideration aligns with the mandate set forth by DOST-PHREB (DOST A.O. no. 001, s. 2007) which directs that all research involving human participants in the Philippines must undergo ethical review by an accredited Research Ethics Committee. It does this by ensuring research is conducted ethically and that the rights of human participants are protected. In addition, this study also adheres to the Data Protection Act of 2012 (RA 10173), which aims to uphold the universal ethical values that safeguard and promote the dignity of people involved in health research. Finally, to ensure full compliance with the ethical considerations set forth by the law and school policies, this study follows the guidelines of HCDC-REC following the nine elements: social value, informed consent, risks, benefits and safety, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualifications of the researcher, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Informed Consent provides the research respondents with the information they need to decide whether to participate in a study. This information includes the purpose of the

study, the procedures involved, the potential risks and benefits, and the participant's right to withdraw from the study at any time. In this study, the respondents were given an informed consent form, which was given to them in two copies: one personally whenever possible and the other through e-mail as a soft copy a week before the interview. This was done to give them time to think and to value their freedom to decline or withdraw. Retrieval and acknowledgment of the signed consent form would be via e-mail or in person. In the case of an e-mail, replying to the e-mail with the participant's complete name in all caps or with an e-signature would be tantamount to giving consent to participate in the study. On the other hand, a signed Informed Consent signifies voluntary participation in the study.

The researcher also ensured the anonymity of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded throughout the whole duration of the conduct of the study. The researcher also ensured that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. Moreover, to avoid plagiarism, the manuscript underwent checking through online plagiarism checker software and was subsequently revised to preserve originality.

By implementing measures to safeguard the privacy and maintain the confidentiality of data, the researcher could effectively contribute to protecting research participants' safety and overall welfare. This approach also fosters trust among participants and upholds the integrity and reliability of the research outcomes. Compliant with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173), the researcher secured the information obtained from the respondents throughout the research.

The researcher also vowed that all the information gathered from the participants would be for research purposes only. Thus, printed and digital copies of the research materials' safety, including the responses and personal data of the participants, were ensured throughout the duration of the study. Printed materials were kept in a safety cabinet/drawer accessible only to the researcher. Digital copies were stored in a password-protected hard drive and were stored in the said cabinet/drawer. All cloud or online copies were deleted promptly after saving or printing. All password-protected copies were encrypted with symbols, upper and lowercase letters, and numbers. Upon the completion of the study, hard copies of research materials were shredded, and online data was totally removed from the hard drive through secured deletion.

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